

SNJEŽANA VASILJEVIĆ, PHD*

EQUALITY, NON-DISCRIMINATION & FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS: OLD HABITS DIE HARD!

Summary:

The non-discrimination principle is the core principle of the internal market of the European Union (EU). It is defined through primary and secondary EU law. The problem of its interpretation lies in the interpretation of direct effect in both vertical and horizontal situations. This paper discusses the key issue of the understanding of fundamental rights protection and the implementation of anti-discrimination legislation.

Key words: *fundamental rights, Court of Justice of the European Union and the European Court of Human Rights, European Convention on Human Rights, EU competences, equality principle*

* Assistant Professor, Chair for European Public Law, Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia, E-mail: snjezana.vasiljevic@pravo.hr

I. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this paper is to reveal how the European legal system protects human rights and to observe the obstacles for the consistent implementation of European equality standards. Further, the paper will discuss how two separate European legal orders operate through the active role of the two European courts. The first section will explore the role of European equality legislation and possible interpretations. The second section will reveal possible challenges faced by fundamental rights protection in times of economic crisis by focusing on the issue of multiple discrimination. The third section will reveal the limits of fundamental rights protection. The final section will focus on a possible way out of the equality law crisis by discussing the direct effect of EU law and a possible way towards the efficient suppression of discrimination.

II. EUROPEAN EQUALITY LAW

European fundamental rights protection is subject to certain limitations. The first anti-discrimination standards were adopted in the 70s, although to date they have not produced revolutionary results. When I say “revolutionary”, I refer to the lack of final judgments before the national courts and clear legal reasoning in balancing between two or more protected fundamental rights. There are several reasons for this. Firstly, the concept of fundamental rights protection was not the core element of the internal market at the beginning of European integration. European primary law was lacking the basic element of fundamental rights protection until first the Maastricht Treaty (1993) and then the Amsterdam Treaty (1999) entered into force. The Amsterdam Treaty revealed the existence of different forms of discrimination which the founding fathers decided to prohibit in its Article 13. Article 13 was the legal basis for the development of the European secondary anti-discrimination legislation. Secondly, anti-discrimination directives have not been transposed fully or correctly into national legal orders. Sometimes, anti-discrimination directives cannot be considered a sufficient tool in the fight against discrimination. Thirdly, the fact that, in general, EU directives do not have a direct effect on private parties reflects negatively on national anti-discrimination frameworks. Fourthly, another possible negative reflection is that human rights protection lies outside the scope of EU law. Nevertheless, there is another safeguard system operated by the Council of Europe. In some European countries (mostly Eastern European countries) reform of the justice system and access to justice are very slow and there is a huge backlog of pending cases.

In the meantime, the European legislature has already developed a system of legal norms and judicial practice which simplify implementation. One possible way out is for the principle of non-discrimination enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights in

Article 21 to open up space for the further development of the application of EU law, as well as for the possible broadening of EU competences. Further, a more active approach by the ECtHR would help strengthen the protection of fundamental rights in Europe.

To begin, it is necessary to outline the background of the principle of equality. Development of EU equality law has undergone turbulent decades of recognition in the EU legal order as well as in national legal orders. The primary goal of the creation of anti-discrimination law was to enable fair competition in the European market.¹ However, the secondary goal was the suppression of sex discrimination and the implementation of social measures. Since 1975, the EU has created a comprehensive anti-discrimination legal and policy framework. This framework has been criticised over the years.² One can notice that the European anti-discrimination concept has lost its primary purpose, since the anti-discrimination model is dominated by a purely individualistic approach that does not solve the problem in the form of structural social discrimination of marginalised groups in society, such as racial and sex discrimination,³ and therefore excludes the implementation of specific (positive) measures that are primarily needed to correct certain social inequality.⁴ The equality and non-discrimination principle is the core principle of the internal market of the European Union. Moreover, it is considered the highest value in all human rights international agreements. The principle of equality and non-discrimination has been of particular importance in European Community law and has now been raised to the level of a general principle. With the entering into force of the Treaty of Maastricht (1993), the modern European Union emerged. Primary and secondary European law on equal opportunities between women and men has developed over the past thirty years in order to eradicate the gender pay gap and gender discrimination in working conditions and social security. Over the years, the practice of the CJEU has helped in the interpretation and implementation of the legal framework for gender discrimination. Today, equality between women and men is recognised as one of the key objectives of the EU in its inclusion of the gender dimension in all activities of the Union.

Building on the experience of the EU in the fight against discrimination on grounds of sex, consensus was reached in the mid-1990s for regulating other forms of discrimination in the European Union, including in European primary and secondary legislation. The result of this process is the inclusion of a new Article 13 in the Treaty of Maastricht. Finally, the EU decided to adopt a general prohibition of discrimination, but for a limited list of

¹ CJEU, Case C-43/75 *Defrenne* [1976]

² M. Bell, "Advancing EU Anti-Discrimination Law: The European Commission's 2008 Proposal for a New Directive," *The Equal Rights Review*, Vol.3, 2009, <http://www.equalrightstrust.org/ertdocumentbank/mark%20bell.pdf>, (accessed 21 November 2015).

³ M. Bell, *Racism and Equality in the European Union*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2008.

⁴ A. D. Freeman, "Legitimizing Racial Discrimination Through Antidiscrimination Law: A Critical Review of Supreme Court Doctrine," *Minnesota Law Review*, vol. 62, 1978, pp. 1049-1119.

protected characteristics. However, the Amsterdam Treaty strengthens the existing provisions on the protection of human rights in the Treaty on European Union (Articles 6 and 7) by introducing a set of principles on which the Union is founded (“freedom, democracy, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms and the rule of law”), giving the CJEU powers to guarantee respect of these principles by the European institutions, and in anticipation of sanctions in the case of violation of the fundamental principles of the Member States.⁵ Article 13 of the Amsterdam Treaty broadened the scope of the prohibition of discrimination by adding more protected characteristics to the existing list: sex, race, ethnicity, disability, age and sexual orientation. This list is exhaustive, which means that it does not allow other protected characteristics to be added. However, those Treaty norms were the kick off for the further development of secondary anti-discrimination legislation. On the other hand, this was also reflected in efforts to create a “European Bill of Rights”. In 1999 the European Council proposed that a “body composed of representatives of the Heads of State and Government and of the President of the Commission as well as of members of the European Parliament and national parliaments” should be formed to draft a Charter of Fundamental Rights (“Charter”). The draft Charter was adopted on 2 October 2000 and it was solemnly proclaimed by the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers and the European Commission on 7 December 2000.⁶

Unfortunately, at the beginning of its existence, the Charter was not legally binding. Its legal status was uncertain until the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon on 1 December 2009. Following the entry into force of the Lisbon Treaty, the Charter has had the same legal value as the European Union treaties. Thus, the Charter has become a powerful weapon in the fight against discrimination. The principle of non-discrimination enshrined in the Charter builds on Article 13 of the Treaty on EU and represents the basis for the further development of EU antidiscrimination legislation.

The adoption of Article 13 is a reflection of the growing recognition of the need to develop a coherent and integrated approach to combat discrimination. The European Commission decided to give effect to the powers set forth in Article 13 and in 1999 adopted a package of proposals. This led to the unanimous adoption of the key directives in 2000 aim-

⁵ Art. 13 of the TEU: “1. Without prejudice to other provisions of this Treaty and within the limits of the powers conferred by it upon the Community, the Council, acting unanimously on a proposal from the Commission and after consulting the European Parliament, may take appropriate action to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation.”

2. By way of derogation from paragraph 1, when the Council adopts Community incentive measures, excluding any harmonisation of the laws and regulations of the Member States in order to contribute to the achievement of the objectives referred to in paragraph 1, it shall act in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 251. Treaty establishing the European Community” (consolidated version 1997), *Official Journal* C 340 of 10 November 1997 <http://eur-lex.europa.edu/en/treaties/index.htm#founding>, (accessed 22 October 2015).

⁶ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, 7 December 2000, Official Journal of the European Communities, 18 December 2000 (OJ C 364/01) <http://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6b3b70.html> (accessed 30 July 2013).

ing at providing effective legal protection against discrimination.⁷ The Racial Equality Directive prohibits direct and indirect discrimination, including incitement to discrimination based on ethnic or racial origin. It covers the area of employment, training, education, social security, health care, housing and access to goods and services. It also prohibits multiple discrimination. However, the CJEU and national case law consider discrimination solely on the basis of the single axis approach.⁸ The single axis approach analyses discrimination on the basis of each of the grounds for discrimination separately. For example, imagine that in the same case we are a victim of discrimination based on gender and also a member of some vulnerable or marginalised group. The courts would probably not have taken into account the fact that discrimination occurred on two or more different bases.⁹ Much of the existing literature exploring multiple discrimination has criticised the single axis approach from a legal perspective (Moon, 2002; Vasiljevic, 2009; Schiek and Lawson, 2011).

In some countries this represented a completely new approach to anti-discrimination legislation and policies based on individual rights. Member States must complement their own legislation on gender equality in the light of the general Equal Treatment Directive,¹⁰ the Directive on Equal Treatment in Employment and Occupation, and the Racial Equality Directive. The Racial Equality Directive is broader in its scope because it covers other areas outside the labour market, such as education, social security, and access to goods and services. This has led to the adoption of national laws covering discrimination on grounds of sex amongst other grounds of discrimination. Moreover, the new Directive introduced the principle of equality between men and women in the access to goods and services and their provision.¹¹ Finally, a political decision was made to bring a new comprehensive directive based on the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment for men and women in employment.¹² The Directive for the first time in many Member States

⁷ Council Directive 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin, OJ L 180, 19.7.2000 and Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation, OJ L 303, 2.12.2000.

⁸ S. Vasiljević, *Similar or Different: Discrimination in the European Union and the Republic of Croatia*, Zagreb, Tim Press, 2011.

⁹ D. Schiek & A. Lawson (eds.), *EU Non-Discrimination Law and Intersectionality: Investigating the Triangle of Racial, Gender and Disability Discrimination*, Ashgate, 2011.

¹⁰ Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002 amending Council Directive 76/207/EEC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions, OJ L 269/15, 5.12.2002.

¹¹ Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services, OJ L 373, 21.12.2004.

¹² Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast), OJ L 204, 26.7.2006.

presented protection against discrimination on the basis of certain grounds. Directives require the introduction of new definitions and legal concepts. In this area, they have also led to the establishment of new specialised equality bodies and to the exercise of the powers of certain existing bodies. Deadlines for the transposition of the Racial Equality Directive and the Employment Equality Directive into national law have already passed; however, the correct implementation of both directives into national law does not exhaust the possibility for natural and legal persons in national courts to refer directly to the individual rights guaranteed by the equality directives. In general, this is possible when the directives are properly implemented in national law, but the application of national law does not achieve the result prescribed by the directives.¹³

All Member States have adopted a unique and comprehensive anti-discrimination framework. There is also a visible and positive trend of single equality bodies dealing with all grounds of discrimination set out in the directives. Such bodies are not the “invention” of the European Commission, because they were established in some countries much earlier (for example in the UK, Netherlands, Sweden). Through the establishment of such bodies, citizens are offered a cheaper and faster alternative to resolve discrimination complaints. Such bodies also strengthen collective awareness of the dangers of discrimination and the need to develop a culture of equal opportunity and non-discrimination. Unfortunately, this kind of institutional protection of human rights is still underutilised.

III. CHALLENGES OF FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS PROTECTION IN TIMES OF ECONOMIC CRISIS

Sometimes anti-discrimination laws can recognise problems arising for certain individuals belonging to vulnerable groups. For example, it can be seen if one experiences discrimination on different grounds in separate cases: if a woman with disabilities does not get promotion solely because she is a woman and if it is also preferred for such a position to go to a male candidate, or in any other situation where her participation in business meetings was prevented because the meetings were held in rooms that do not have access for people with disabilities. In such situations, courts deal separately with certain grounds of discrimination. Such cases of discrimination arise from a situation where, for example, there are different requirements in a job description advertised for candidates where the absence of one of the conditions would reduce the chances of securing the job, and, in the case of the lack of more specific characteristics, the chance of winning a particular work position further decreases. The United Kingdom is one of the few Member States

¹³ The deadline for the transposition of Directive 2000/43/EZ expired on 19 July 2003. The deadline for the transposition of Directive 2000/78/EZ expired on 2 December 2003. Some Member States have used the possibility to request an additional period up to three years to adopt provisions relating to discrimination based on age and disability, Case C-62/00 *Marks & Spencer* [2002] ECR I-6325.

which has a wide variety of special legislation to combat discrimination (the Sex Discrimination Act 1975, the Equal Pay Act, 1976, the Protection against Harassment Act 1997, the Equality Act, 2006, etc.). In the UK, in the case of *Perera v. Civil Service Commission* (No. 2),¹⁴ Mr Perera, who was born in Sri Lanka, claimed that he had been rejected on a number of occasions for jobs in the Civil Service on the grounds of his colour or national origin. After having been granted discovery of limited documents by the Employment Appeal Tribunal [1980] IRLR 233, his case was heard on its merits by an Industrial Tribunal. The case of Ms. Perera was the case of multiple discrimination but in his case multiple discrimination was not recognised by courts.

African-American women first spoke out about the ways in which single-ground approaches to anti-discrimination law failed to capture the lived realities of inequalities linked to gender, race and ethnicity.¹⁵ Discrimination becomes more visible in times of economic crisis and women are mostly affected by its consequences. During economic crises, “it is more likely that the members of disadvantaged groups are made redundant first”¹⁶ Multiple discrimination continues to be deeply affected by international relations and political developments after September 11th.¹⁷ As Sheppard claims (2011: 2), “ongoing tensions around national security, religious diversity, race and gender have led to growing controversies around racial profiling (predominantly affecting racialised Muslim men) and religious dress codes in the workplace (affecting predominantly racialised Muslim women).”¹⁸ In these contexts, it is impossible to separate the overlapping strands of exclusion linked to national and ethnic origin, race, religion, and gender.¹⁹ Research has shown that inequality at work is often experienced on more than one ground at the same

¹⁴ *Perera v. Civil Service Commission* (no 2) [1983] ICR428.

¹⁵ K. Crenshaw, “Demarginalizing the Intersection Between Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Anti-discrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Anti-Racist Politics”, in *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 1989, pp. 139-167; see also, J. Conaghan, “Intersectionality and the Feminist Project in Law”, in E. Grabham et al, *Intersectionality and Beyond – Law, Power and the Politics of Location*, New York, Routledge-Cavendish, 2009, pp. 21-48 at pp. 22-24 and pp. 35-38.

¹⁶ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *The Impact of the Racial Equality Directive - Views of Trade Unions and Employers in the European Union: Strengthening the Fundamental Rights Architecture in the EU IV*, Luxembourg, 2010, p. 45.; C. Sheppard, “Multiple Discrimination in the World of Work,” Working Paper No. 66, International Labour Organisation, 2011.

¹⁷ C. M. Gandara, “Post-9/11 Backlash Discrimination in the Workplace: Employers Beware of Potential Double Recovery”, in *Houston Business and Tax Journal*, Vol. 7, 2006, pp. 169-200. See also, S. Estreicher and M. Bodie (eds.), “Workplace Discrimination Privacy and Security in an Age of Terrorism”, *Proceedings of the New York University 55th Annual Conference on Labor Workplace Discrimination in an Age of Terrorism*, Aspen Publishers, 2007.

¹⁸ C. Sheppard, *Multiple Discrimination in the World of Work*, Working Paper No. 66, International Labour Organisation, 2011.

¹⁹ D. Schiek and V. Chege, *European Union Non-discrimination Law: Comparative Perspectives on Multidimensional Equality Law*, London, New York, Routledge-Cavendish, 2009.

time.²⁰ The result of growing inequalities at the workplace is a violation of human dignity and a risk of further limitations of human rights. “To prevent this risk, new concepts and approaches are needed to address the realities of multiple and overlapping inequalities and vulnerability at work.”²¹ Multiple discrimination in particular cases is not recognised. A part of the problem lies in the fact that the formal prerequisite for proving discrimination depends of the existence of a comparator. Direct discrimination is the unfavourable treatment of a person because of certain characteristics. There are two methods of proof: the procedural and analytical approach and the comparative approach. In addition, it is my opinion that direct discrimination wrongly restricts the comparative method of proof with regard to establishing less favourable treatment concerning a person who is in the same conditions as other “innocent” people. In contrast, indirect discrimination is a situation where an apparently neutral standard has a less favourable impact on members of a group (the *Bilka* case).²² The problem of indirect discrimination includes the practice, policy or rule applied to a certain group of people in the same way regardless of who they are. For example, there is a rule that all employees must enter the company’s building from the front door. This is a neutral rule, which affects everyone who works for the particular employer. This group is called the pool for comparison. Within this group, some people with a particular protected characteristic may be indirectly discriminated by the neutral rule. For example, if you are a person with disabilities, you cannot enter the company’s building from the front door if the entrance is not accessible. It does not matter if there are no other people with disabilities. There can still be indirect discrimination if something would normally disadvantage people sharing your characteristic. In cases of direct and indirect discrimination, courts recognise discrimination only on a legitimate ground (e.g. either sex or race). Looking at the problem at the horizontal and vertical levels, we can see that the law allows comparison only at the purely horizontal (women and black women and white women) or exclusively at the vertical level (a black woman and a black man). Comparing the bias level is not permitted (black women and white men).

This is a real problem, which can be displayed graphically based on these cases:

1. The comparison of a black woman doing military service with a male black man does not have to show the discrimination she experienced as it will be proven even through a comparison with a white woman. Black men do not need to have problems with military service and neither do white women. However, in this particular case, black women can face discriminatory behaviour. In order to prove this, it is

²⁰ P. Uccellari, “Multiple Discrimination: How Law Can Reflect Reality,” in *The Equal Rights Review*, 2008, Vol. 1, pp. 24-49 at p. 29.

²¹ C. Sheppard, “Multiple Discrimination in the World of Work,” Working Paper No. 66, International Labour Organisation, 2011.

²² CJEU, Case C-170/84 *Bilka Kaufhaus GmbH v Weber von Hartz* [1986]

necessary to allow a comparison with multiple effects in relation to ethnicity and gender/sex.

2. Also, a comparison of the experiences of a woman of Islamic faith with those of a man of Islamic faith does not have to show the level of discrimination. However, comparison with a woman of the Christian faith may show possible discrimination. In order to observe the true dimension of discrimination, it is necessary to include in this case religion and gender.
3. The case of boy members of the Afro-Caribbean race that were expelled from school compared to a similar case of girls of the Afro-Caribbean race may reveal only gendered aspect of discrimination, but not the racial experience of discrimination. So, again, it is necessary to include gender and race.
4. Similarly, we can for example take a male homosexual who is HIV positive and who is fired from his place of work on account of this. Perhaps the employer would not have acted if it was an HIV-positive heterosexual person. The real reason may be proven only when we take into account the full experience of discrimination, taking into account gender, sexual orientation and state of health.

In Britain, in the *Bahl v Law Society* case,²³ the mentioned problems could be observed. Ms Bahl, a woman of Asian descent, claimed to be a victim of discrimination based on gender and race. In the first stage of the case, the Employment Tribunal decided that her situation could be compared to a white man so as to take into account both the characteristics of race and gender. However, the labour court and the appeal court decided that this was not possible and that it was an incorrect interpretation of the law. On appeal, Judge Lord Peter Gibson said: “In our judgment, it was necessary for the EAT to find the primary facts in relation to each type of discrimination against each alleged discriminator and then to explain why it was making the inference, which it did in favour of Dr Bahl on whom lay the burden of proving her case. It failed to do so, and thereby, as the EAT correctly found, erred in law”. As can be seen from this point of view and from the judgment of the Court of Appeal, it is considered necessary to separately consider each form of discrimination if the plaintiff claims that all the grounds for discrimination intermingle. In cases of direct discrimination such as *Bahl*, it is necessary to determine whether there was less favourable treatment in relation to the treatment of any other person with similar characteristics as the plaintiff. The comparison may be a real person, if one exists, and, if not, the comparator may be a hypothetical person.²⁴ In court practice it is first necessary to determine whether there is unfavourable treatment in relation to the comparator (the “less favourable treatment” issue) and whether the unfavourable treatment is the only relevant reason (the “reason why” issue). In summary, the above case leads to the conclusion that European

²³ *Bahl v. Law Society* [2004] IRLR 799.

²⁴ This is explained in *Shamoon v. Chief Constable of the Royal Ulster Constabulary*.

legislation is not sufficiently effective to protect against discrimination because it does not provide comprehensive legal protection based on a combination of multiple experiences of discrimination that is indivisible and therefore deserves special treatment not only because it is an issue of equal opportunities but also a multi-dimensional experience that deserves special attention within the scope of the protection of fundamental human rights.

There is no case in front of the CJEU or the ECtHR on the issue of multiple discrimination. When it comes to discrimination, the CJEU has a long practice of deciding in cases related to the labour market because of its limited competences, as well as the limited scope of the equality directives. The exception from the labour market is Directive 2004/113/EC implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services which enshrines in EU law the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services. All EU countries were required to implement the directive by the end of 2007. A specific exception was also foreseen for insurance and related financial services where gender was used as a determining factor in the assessment of risk based on relevant and accurate actuarial and statistical data. However, the Court of Justice of the European Union annulled Article 5(2) of the Directive in its *Test Achats* ruling. The ruling obliged Member States to make unisex premiums and benefits mandatory by 21 December 2012. Since this date, the unisex rule has applied without derogation in relation to the calculation of individuals' premiums and benefits in new contracts.²⁵ On the other hand, the ECtHR protects fundamental rights in all spheres of life but as a "European constitutional court", after all legal remedies have been exhausted before national courts.

IV. LIMITS OF EUROPEAN FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS PROTECTION

European human rights legislation provides different levels of protection. Human rights protection in Europe has two separate supranational legal foundations. The first is the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR), operating under the auspices of the Council of Europe (CoE), and with the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) as the final judicial body to hear and settle alleged violations of the Convention by the CoE's 47 Member States. The second is the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union

²⁵ CJEU, Case C-236/09 *Test Achats* [2011], the Grand Chamber ruled that a provision which enabled States to maintain sex-specific insurance premiums, notwithstanding the rule on unisex insurance and benefits laid down in Directive 2004/113, was incompatible with the principle of sex equality, enshrined in Articles 21 and 23 of the Charter. The Court took the unusual step of delaying the entry into force of the judgment until the expiry of an "appropriate transitional period", allowing insurance companies time to adjust to the ruling. See more at: <http://europeanlawblog.eu/?p=1384#sthash.cVMmclxl.dpuf>, (accessed 15 November 2015).

(TFEU) and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (EU Charter) that was promulgated by the 2009 Lisbon Treaty. However, the legal order of the EU, interpreted by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), creates a new arena for the further development of fundamental rights protection.

Given that all EU Member States are also members of the Council of Europe, it would appear that there is no need for two sources of European human rights law being enforced by two separate legal institutions. Moreover, this might cause confusion in determining the level of fundamental rights protection. One might conclude that two separate legal jurisdictions over human rights might create double standards or, even worse, legal uncertainty. The CJEU and the ECtHR have jurisdiction over different human rights instruments even though their territorial jurisdiction overlaps. The concern is that this engenders two different bodies of law, thereby subjecting European states to dual, and possibly contradictory, treaty obligations, which may not be uniformly interpreted because of the divergences in the respective functions and mandates of the CJEU and the ECtHR. The ECtHR delivers judgments against Member States of the Council of Europe on alleged violations of the European human rights treaties. Complaints may be lodged by individuals or by other Member States. This mechanism works very well and individuals are quite active in their efforts to achieve justice.²⁶ The CJEU has limited competences and its focus is on the interpretation of its primary and secondary law.

First of all, it is very important to emphasise the supreme character of EU law.²⁷ This means that you cannot depart from EU law by a subsequent national law. From the very beginning, constitutional courts of the Member States were not ready to accept the supreme character of EU law. In the *Handelsgesellschaft* case,²⁸ the Court decided that the respect for fundamental rights was part of the general principles that have to be obeyed. In this case, the so-called 'Solange' problem arose. The German court finally agreed that EU law prevailed as long as its protection was better. In cases where German national protection was better, German law would still be applicable. Next to this supreme character, EU law can be directly applicable. To explain in which circumstances it can be directly applicable, I have to make a distinction between primary law and secondary law. Primary law encompasses the treaties (TEU and TFEU), general principles (which includes fundamental rights) and constitutional rights (Art 2 TEU). Secondary law includes international agreements, directives, recommendations, regulations and opinions. Secondary law can only have direct effect when it meets three requirements, namely, the text has to be sufficiently clear, unconditional and not requiring other legal actions. The direct effect of EU law enables an

²⁶ E. Voeten, Politics, Judicial Behavior and Institutional Design, in Jonas Christoffersen, Mikael Rask Madsen (eds), *The European Court of Human Rights Between Law and Politics*, OUP, 2011, pp. 62.

²⁷ CJEU, Case C-6/64 *Costa v ENEL* [1964]; Case C-29/69 *Stauder* [1969].

²⁸ CJEU, Case C-11/70 *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft mbH v Einfuhr- und Vorratsstelle für Getreide und Futtermittel* [1970]

individual of a Member State to rely on, for example, the treaties before national tribunals and national courts. Now, we have arrived at the difference between vertical and horizontal effect. Horizontal effect is about the presence of EU law between one natural person or legal entity and another natural person or legal entity. Normally, horizontal effect is not really a common thing because it can cause damage to individuals. In its early practice, the CJEU confirmed that norms of the founding treaties could have a direct effect in horizontal situations. This was confirmed in the case of *Defrenne vs. Sabena*.²⁹ This case was about a difference in wages between a man and a woman in the company Sabena. The principle of equality means that a man and woman should be paid in an equal way for the same job. Because of the direct effect of Article 119 of the EEC Treaty, individuals can rely on it before national courts, even though the Member State has not transposed the provisions into national law. The CJEU has confirmed the importance of the prohibition on gender discrimination in many cases; however, it has always linked it to the general principle of equal treatment (the principle was already established in the Treaty of Rome of 1957 (Art 119 of the 1957 EEC Treaty) and now this principle is prescribed in Art 157 TFEU), which is recognised as a fundamental norm of EU law. For four decades, EU actions in this field of discrimination were limited to sex discrimination in the workplace. With the entry into force of the Amsterdam Treaty, the EU obtained a clear legal basis for combating discrimination, which is currently enshrined in Art 19 TFEU on a number of grounds other than sex. In 2000, two directives were adopted: the Employment Equality Directive,³⁰ prohibiting discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation, religious beliefs, age and disability in the area of employment; and the Racial Equality Directive. This was a great expansion of the scope of non-discrimination law under the EU. Later, when the Treaty of Lisbon entered into force in 2009, the Charter of Fundamental Rights became a legally binding document. As a result, EU institutions are bound to it and Member States are also bound when implementing EU law. Specifically, Art 21³¹ of the Charter contains prohibition on various grounds. This means that individuals can complain about EU legislation or national legislation that implements EU law if they feel the Charter has not been respected.

Since then, the CJEU went even further when examining direct effect of directives in horizontal situations. The CJEU stated that a direct provision of a directive could only

²⁹ CJEU, Case C-43/75 *Defrenne* [1976]

³⁰ Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32000L0078:en:HTML>, (accessed 30 November 2015).

³¹ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2000, Article 21 - Non-discrimination: "Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited" http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf, (accessed 30 November 2015).

have horizontal effect if no positive obligation for the individual arises.³² But there are some exceptions when it comes to fundamental rights. There are several examples in EU law concerning the horizontal effect of a directive in cases of discrimination based on the principle of equality of the Charter. The *Kukukdeveci* case³³ considered a German national who was discriminated against based on her age. A notice period was based on the amount of years of service, but the years before the age of 25 were not taken into account. Discrimination can only be justified if there is an objective, reasonable and legitimate aim. The principle of equal treatment could not be justified and was violated in this case because people who started working before the age of 25 are discriminated against compared to people who started working later than the age of 25. As long as the content, in this case, of a directive, consolidates a fundamental principle, the horizontal effect can cause the non-application of the national law which was not in accordance with EU law. Regarding horizontal direct effect, it has to be emphasised that directives, unlike regulations or decisions, will always require further implementation on the part of Member States, for which Member States have considerable discretion. However, even if the provision of a directive cannot directly replace the normally applicable national law/provision in determining the outcomes of a dispute in horizontal situations (between individuals), a directive may still produce indirect effects. The CJEU has confirmed this in its recent cases (*Mangold* and *Kukudeveci*). The fact that a directive, which is a secondary source of EU law, provides that direct age discrimination could be justified in connection with other grounds, Art 6(1) of the Charter leaves some questions for this ground of discrimination to be regarded as a fundamental human right. But knowing that this ground is recognised under Art 21 of the Charter, the CJEU jurisprudence confirms it.

In *Mangold*, *Bartsch*³⁴ and *Kukudeveci*, the CJEU extended the scope of the equal treatment principle and included all the non-discrimination grounds set out in the 2000 directives. These three judgments reaffirmed and clarified the relationship that exists between the 2000 directives, the general principle of equal treatment and the provisions of the Charter.³⁵ Later, the CJEU made it clear that the directives should not only be read as simply setting minimum standards, but also that they provide real protection against discrimination. This was developed in *Firma Feryn*,³⁶ *Coleman*,³⁷ and *Meister*³⁸ which con-

³² CJEU, Case C-201/02 *Wells* [2004]

³³ Case C-555/07 *Kücükdeveci* [2010] ECR I-365

³⁴ CJEU, Case C-427/06 *Bartsch* [2008] ECR I-7245.

³⁵ C. O'Conneide, European Network of Legal Experts in the non-discrimination field, "The Evolution and Impact of the Case-Law of the Court of Justice of the European Union on Directives 2000/43/EC and 2000/78/EC", 2012, p. 17.

³⁶ CJEU, Case C-54/07 *Centrum voor Gelijkheid van Kansen en voor Racismebestrijding* [2008] ECR I-5187.

³⁷ CJEU, Case C-303/06 *Coleman* [2008] ECR I-5603, para. 47-48.

³⁸ CCJEU, Case C-415/10 *Meister* [2012]

cerned direct discrimination. These cases clarified the scope of prohibition of direct discrimination and indicated that the directives should not be read in a narrow or excessively formal manner. In sum, all these developments increasingly clarify the non-discrimination principle in EU law.

After referring to the CJEU's judgments (*Mangold* and *Küküdeveci*), it is clear that the Charter made it possible for private parties to rely on it and that it was applicable in horizontal situations, which would give the same possibility in our case. To confirm this, the CJEU went on in the *AMS* case to distinguish *AMS* from *Küküdeveci*, ruling that "the principle of non-discrimination on grounds of age at issue in that case, laid down in Article 21(1) of the Charter, is sufficient in itself to confer on individuals an individual right which they may invoke as such".³⁹ Of course, the CJEU remains reluctant to agree that all rights are directly horizontally applicable and have a test for this, which is used to determine whether this is so. The provision has to be intended to confer rights on individuals and has to be sufficiently clear and precise.

As Sever (2014) claims, "the Court of Justice has developed its case law on the horizontal effect of the Charter by interpreting the directives particularly in the area of employment law or by adjudicating on their validity with the Charter. Despite the wording of Article 51(1) of the Charter which governs the Charter's scope of application, and according to which individuals may invoke fundamental rights vis-à-vis the institutions, bodies, offices and agencies of the Union and the Member States only when they are implementing Union law, the Court of Justice has interpreted it broadly and has held in a number of cases that certain provisions of the Charter directly apply in relationships between individuals".⁴⁰

Further, in the future, one may expect an increase of cases where the Court of Justice is confronted with situations which raise the question of the right to rely, in proceedings between private persons, on directives which contribute to ensuring observance of fundamental rights, since among the fundamental rights contained in the Charter are a number which are already part of the existing body of EU law in the form of directives.⁴¹ As Seifert (2012) claims, horizontal effect is intended to provide a minimum of social justice in the private relations of individuals in order to guarantee basic fairness to the 'weaker' party.⁴²

One can argue that the horizontal effect of the Charter provisions as expressions of a general principle of law and which have been made concrete with directives is compensation for the lack of horizontal effect of directives. In this sense, Advocate General Bot opines

³⁹ CJEU, Case C-176/12 *Association de médiation sociale* [2014], para. 47.

⁴⁰ S. Sever, "Horizontal Effect and the Charter", *Croatian Yearbook of European Law and Policy*, 2014.

⁴¹ A. Seifert, 'L'effet horizontal des droits fondamentaux', *Revue Trimestrielle de Droit Européen*, vol. 48, no. 4, p. 801, 2012.

⁴² A. Seifert, 'L'effet horizontal des droits fondamentaux', *Revue Trimestrielle de Droit Européen*, vol. 48, no. 4, p. 801, 2012.

in *Kücükdeveci*⁴³ that when it is apparent that the national legislation in question implementing a directive is contrary to EU law, it is not contested that the national court, within the limits of its jurisdiction, has to ensure the full effectiveness of EU law when it determines the dispute before it.⁴⁴ Traditionally, the principle of equality binds the Union institutions and also the Member States, where they implement, or act within the scope of, EU law. In certain circumstances, it may bind natural and legal persons. This occurs in particular in the areas of prohibition of discrimination on grounds of nationality and sex discrimination.⁴⁵

Indeed, the horizontal effect of fundamental rights of the EU concerning the application of the general principle of equality – the principle of equal pay and prohibition of discrimination on grounds of nationality – existed in the primary law of the EU and was, therefore, legally binding before the adoption of the Charter. So, the horizontal effect of these provisions was, when the Charter was adopted, a well-established rule rather than an exception. Moreover, since corresponding provisions also exist in the Charter, the horizontal effect is also recognised for the latter provisions. In any case, it would be paradoxical if the introduction of the Charter reduced the protection of fundamental rights in primary law.⁴⁶

CJEU case law, as shown above, already stated that general principles such as equal treatment are derived from the constitutional traditions of European Member States. Fundamental rights are also enshrined in the Charter, and they have to be basically protected because they result from the constitutional traditions common to the Member States, because they are not new, but founded on the basis of 'established laws', such as Community Treaties, the constitutional principles common to the Member States, the European Convention on Human Rights and the Social Charters of the EU and the Council of Europe.

V. EQUALITY PRINCIPLE - STUCK BETWEEN TWO EUROPEAN COURTS?

In the EU, there is a tendency towards universal interpretation of the principle of equality, but after decades of introducing the principle of equal pay for equal work, the rhetorical question arises of where are we now? As a result of these changes, inequality has increased both within and between nation-states; a feminisation of labour has escalated; and an extreme xenophobic right wing has become established in many European countries. In addition, the EU equality directives provide protection for a limited list of reasons for discrimination. Despite the fact that Member States can enhance their nation-

⁴³ Case C-555/07 *Kücükdeveci* [2010] ECR I-365, Opinion of AG Bot, paras. 57-70.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, para 48.

⁴⁵ T. Tridimas, *The General Principles of EU Law*, 2nd edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2007, pp. 74-75.

⁴⁶ CJEU, Case C-176/12 *Association de médiation sociale* [2014], Opinion of AG Cruz Villalón, paras. 34-35.

al legislation and add more specific anti-discrimination provisions, in a number of countries the national legislation has not even been fully aligned with European Union law. The possible way out of today's political and nationalistic turbulence is the application of both legislative and non-legislative measures (e.g. comprehensive anti-discrimination policies, social inclusion, tolerance towards migrants and asylum seekers, etc.).

The window through which the protection of fundamental rights entered into the anti-discrimination legal framework was the development of general legal principles of the European Community. The constitutional traditions of the Member States has also entered the legal system of Community law,⁴⁷ and the CJEU has attributed special importance to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR) but not in terms of actual incorporation, because the CJEU implies only legal acts of the Union. The CJEU monitors the legality of the actions of the EU and in an indirect way examines violations of fundamental rights. When it comes to discrimination, both courts seek to coordinate jurisprudence, and the CJEU in its practice often refers to the judgments of the ECtHR. The CJEU has also been clear that EU law takes precedence over all other claims of international law and the decisions of other international tribunals.⁴⁸ Although the European Union has not yet acceded to the ECHR, the Convention is often a source of inspiration for the CJEU when designing the fundamental principles of EU law.⁴⁹ The CJEU has held that the substantive fundamental rights provisions of the ECHR themselves express and reflect existing general principles of EU law. And this line of CJEU case law is now reflected in the terms of Article 6(3) of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) which states that “fundamental rights, as guaranteed by the ECHR and as they result from the constitutional traditions common to the Member States, shall constitute general principles of the Union’s law”. As general principles, the claims of fundamental rights are binding on the EU institutions, and on the Member States when acting within the sphere of EU law.⁵⁰ The CJEU holds itself to be the European Supreme Court, finally and authoritatively interpreting – at least for the EU Member States – the provisions of the ECHR when its provisions arise within a field also covered by EU law. However, as Weiler notes, “Accepting supremacy of Community law without some guarantee that this supreme law would not violate rights fundamental to

⁴⁷ The CJEU's landmark case *Nold v Commission* of 1974 (Case 4/73 *Nold v Commission* [1974] ECR 491, § 13) where the Court held that the rights set out in the European Convention on Human Rights were protected by the Community legal order.

⁴⁸ CJEU joined Cases C-402/05 P *Kadi* [2008] and C415/05 P *Yusuf and Al Barakaat Foundation* [2008]. Compare, however, T-85/09 *Kadi v Commission* [2010], paras. 115-21.

⁴⁹ Case C-555/07 *Küçükdeveci* [2010] ECR I-365

⁵⁰ ECtHR, *Chaplin v. the United Kingdom*, Application No. 59842/10, 4 September 2012; ECtHR, *Eweida v. the United Kingdom*, Application No. 48420/10, 4 September 2012; ECtHR, *Ladele v. the United Kingdom*, Application No. 51671/10, 4 September 2012; ECtHR, *McFarlane v. the United Kingdom*, Application No. 36516/10, 4 September 2012.

the legal patrimony of an individual Member State would be virtually impossible” (1991: 2418). In relation to fundamental rights issues falling within EU law, the Member States of the EU are to regard themselves as simultaneously bound by two different masters: the CJEU (under and in terms of the EU Treaties) and the ECtHR (under and in terms of the ECHR). But these two European courts do not always stand in the same position. They used to have a different interpretation of the following issues: the existence and extent of the privilege against self-incrimination under ECHR, Art 6(1); whether business premises are covered by the ECHR; the right to respect for private life (Art 8); whether the protections of the ECHR could be prayed in aid in relation to the dissemination of information relating to the availability of abortion in other States (Art 10); and whether sexual orientation was a prohibited ground of discrimination under reference to ECHR (Art 14).⁵¹ This burning issue creates confusion in national legal orders and places the courts of the Member States in a difficult position.

Whereas the primary role of the CJEU has been to foster European economic integration, the role of the ECtHR has been to serve as a human rights guardian. Compared to the CJEU’s integrative function, the ECtHR’s role is distinctly different. Although meant to reinforce a common set of rights (specifically drawing inspiration from the Universal Declaration of Human Rights),⁵² the ECHR that was ratified on 4 November 1950 by the Council of Europe was not meant to serve as an exclusively integrative tool. Rather, it was meant to serve as a minimum standard of human rights protections beyond which diversity in Member State practices would be tolerated (O’Donnell 1982). In interpreting the ECHR, Joseph Weiler argues that “When there is a diverse constitutional practice among the Convention States [...] the Court needs to listen, not only preach”, because the “European landscape [...] is a unique and uniquely promising model of tolerance and pluralism” (2010: 1-2). The ECtHR’s purpose, then, is not integrative; in interpreting the Convention, its role is to seek a careful balance between observing a minimal standard of human rights protections and preserving the diverse practices that add texture to the European social landscape. Put differently, if the function of the CJEU is to help build unity through standardisation and harmonisation, the function of the ECtHR is to help build community by forging interdependence where commonalities exist and protecting pluralism where consensus is lacking. However, the ECtHR can only adjudicate in individual cases and impose fines on the violating state. This means that, unlike the CJEU, the

⁵¹ ECtHR, *Schalk and Kopf v. Austria*, Application no. 30141/04. The Court explicitly noted that if and when the ECtHR does recognise the fundamental right of same-sex couples to marry, it would be because a majority of European states already observe marriage equality.

⁵² The preamble of the ECHR notes: “Considering the Universal Declaration of Human Rights proclaimed by the General Assembly of the United Nations on 10 December 1948 [...] Being resolved, as the Governments of European countries which are like-minded and have a common heritage of political traditions, ideals, freedom and the rule of law to take the first steps for the collective enforcement of certain of the Rights stated in the Universal declaration...” Full text available at: <http://www.hri.org/docs/ECHR50.html>, (accessed 15 November 2015).

ECtHR cannot strike down Member State laws. Further, the ECtHR has developed the “margin of appreciation,” which endows state parties to the ECHR with some discretion in incorporating the Convention’s requirements within their domestic legal orders.⁵³ The existence of two distinct means of reference to fundamental rights, either under direct reference to the ECHR or under reference to the general principles of EU law, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights, creates the possibility of conflict for national courts between competing fundamental rights considerations and interpretations.

⁵³ To this end, it cited its 1998 *Petrovic v. Austria* judgment, which held that “the scope of the margin of appreciation will vary according to the circumstances [...] in this respect, one of the relevant factors may be the existence or non existence of common ground between the laws of the Contracting States”.